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EFFECT OF CREATIVE-TEACHING ON CREATIVE-THINKING-FLUENCY AMONG DIFFERENT-ABILITY UPPER-BASIC SCIENCE STUDENTS IN GBOKO, BENUE STATE

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Abstract

Effect of Creative-Teaching (CT) on Creative-Thinking-Fluency (CTF) among different-ability upper-basic science students in Gboko, Benue State was studied using pre-test post-test quasi-experimental design. Two research questions and two null hypotheses guided the study. Out of the 674 students in the seven government grant aided upper-basic schools in Gboko town, a multistage sample of 70 students in two schools was drawn for the study. Torrance Test of Creative Thinking with reliability coefficient of 0.83 determined using a test-retest method and Pearson Product Moment Correlation was used for data collection. Data were analysed using mean and ANCOVA. Findings showed no significant difference in the CTF among different-ability students within the teaching methods, $F(2, 63) = 0.408$, $p(0.667) > 0.05$. However, those taught Basic Science using CT exhibited significantly higher CTF than those in the Lecture Method. $F(1, 63) = 5.338$, $p(0.024) < 0.05$. Moreso, no significant difference existed in the students' CTF based on gender $F(2, 63) = 2.134$, $p(0.127) > 0.05$. Thus, CT was recommended for teaching science at basic schools.

Keywords: Creative-Teaching (CT), Creative-Thinking-Fluency (CTF), Different-Ability and Gender.

Introduction

Generally, human beings are creative in nature. That is why most times if given the opportunity they would like to display their level of creative thinking in handling issues and solving problems. This display of discretion in creativity is common among children. This suggests that young learners are disposed to creative ways of learning. Cheng (as cited in Pen, 2019) interviewed Hong Kong secondary school students after a program in which teachers integrated creative learning instruction into regular science classes for about 4-6 months and found that students felt enjoyment and satisfaction with these kinds of teaching strategies. The instructors used less rote learning, fewer lectures and were focused on activities, practice, participation, and classmate interaction. The students confirmed that they had more opportunities to appreciate other students' creative ideas, to think more broadly from different perspectives, and to explore ideas in which they were interested. However, they rarely mentioned Creative-Thinking-Fluency. Despite the National Policy on Education (FRN, 2013) objectives of science education which ought to: develop interest in science and technology, acquire Basic Science and technology skills, apply scientific and technological knowledge and skills to meet individual and societal needs, take advantage of the career opportunities offered by science and technology and become equipped for future studies in them. These laudable goals may hardly be attained if students' Creative-Thinking-Fluency is not nurtured by suitable teaching.

From experienced, Nigerian students perceived that their mistakes are not generally accepted by their teachers and that they needed more special support or praise for their Creative-Thinking-Fluency. Similarly, university students in Mainland, China also expressed a strong preference for teaching strategies that generate Creative-Thinking-Fluency and facilitate collaboration (Peng, 2019). This implies that students generally prefer Creative-Thinking-Fluency (CTF) to be integrated in the teaching/learning processes. However, they need more specific techniques to guide their Creative-Thinking-Fluency process. In addition, they need support for and acceptance of their creative thoughts. Hence the need to examine effect of Creative-Teaching (CT) on Creative-Thinking-Fluency among different-ability upper-basic science students in Gboko, Benue State.

Creative-Teaching (CT) is tending to create classroom instruction excellently and in a novel fashion. According to Ayua (2019), it involves teaching creatively and teaching for creativity, which in turn enhances Creative-Thinking-Fluency in students with different-ability. Teaching creatively entails demonstrating how to think creatively and the ability to use diverse methodological approaches and resources. While teaching for creativity, it involves inspiring students to think innovatively, exposing them to Creative-Thinking-Fluency for generating ideas, encouraging creative learning and identifying learners' creative strengths as well as fostering them (Ayua, Terhemba & Ikyernum, 2022). Paul E. Torrance is one of the prominent scholars of creativity who severally explored the teaching and learning of creativity (Worwood, 2011). Torrance identified particular skills related to creativity and showed success in creativity teaching using Torrance Incubation Model (TIM) of Creative-Teaching and learning. The model was designed to make teaching more effective in any subject, at any age level (Ayua, 2019). Torrance and Safter (as cited in Ayua, Terhemba & Ikyernum, 2022) submitted that Torrance Incubation Model of Creative-Teaching can be applied to a lesson unit or project in any subject including Basic Science education and at any school level of school to cultivate Creative-Thinking-Fluency in students with different ability.

Creative thinking involves students learning to generate and apply new ideas in specific contexts, seeing existing situations in a new way, identifying alternative explanations, and seeing or making new links that generate a positive novel outcome. This includes combining parts to form original, sifting and refining ideas to discover possibilities, constructing theories and objects, and acting on intuition (Ton, Loc, Uyen & Son, 2020). That is why Guilford (as cited in Nilsson, 2012) noted five aspects of creative thinking which were used as divergent thinking in lieu of creative thinking. These include: fluency, originality, elaboration, abstractness of titles and resistance to premature closure. Therefore, the purpose of this study is to determine the effect of Creative-Teaching on Creative-Thinking-Fluency among different-ability upper-basic science students in Gboko, Benue State.

Creative-Thinking-Fluency (CTF) is the speed and ease of generating new creative ideas or how many different responses produced within a specific time frame. Fluency is the ability to produce many verbal or non-verbal ideas (Pen, 2019). Fluency refers to the quantity of ideas a participant generates (Dumas & Dunbar, 2014). It is pertinent to examine how many ideas Nigerian students can generate in order to prepare them for the challenging tasks in this era and for future visions. In research pertaining to divergent thinking and creativity, tasks are most often scored and operationalized in terms of Fluency (Plucker & Makel, 2010). Indeed, Fluency scores have often solely been used to represent divergent thinking, or even creativity in general (Dumas & Dunbar, 2014). Fluency can be operationalized objectively and easily by counting the number of ideas that a participant generates. These count scores can be further analysed using a variety of statistical procedures, and have demonstrated their usefulness in

testing hypotheses related to divergent thinking and creativity (Dumas & Dunbar, 2014). However, while Fluency scores account for the quantity of ideas that a participant generates on a divergent thinking task, it is therefore, a matter to investigate it among different ability upper-basic students.

Different-ability levels in this study refer to students' high, average and low educational performance based on past academic scores in Basic Science. Ayua (2021); Ayua, Terhemba and Ikyerum (2022) stated that students vary in their academic abilities due to one reason or the other; which may be learner, teacher or environmental based. Hostetter (2013) explained that different academic ability grouping as placing students of differing ability levels in the same class or group. Maikano (2016) also held that ability grouping is based on educators' judgments of students' abilities; and that when assigning students' to tracks, prior test scores or other performance measures provided from other grades or schools are used to determine the ability levels even in gender difference.

Gender difference is the character of being male or female. Gender disparity according to Danjuma (2015) globally militates against equitable participation of boys and girls in Science Education especially in Africa. In a study "Impact of Creative-Teaching on science pupils' academic performance. Ali, Ozovehe and Dyaji (2014) discovered that females rather than males face a number of inequitable difficulties that limit their potentials in participation in the Sciences. This implies that gender peculiarities affect teaching, learning and creativity of students in Basic Science.

Basic Science is a core subject offered at the basic education level in Nigeria, which encompasses the process of Creative-Thinking-Fluency. The subject gives students the opportunity to integrate concepts and processes in the real word (Ndinechi & Okafor, 2016). This implies that Basic Science should be integrated in a way that would enhance students' Creative-Thinking-Fluency for functional living in the 21st century. That is why the Federal Ministry of Education (FME, 2014) posits that Basic Science is an activity-based course. However, these objectives and the relevant of Creative-Thinking-Fluency are still difficult to achieve due to poor teaching method (Sagiru, 2015). Ode, Ayua and Alabi (2019) stated that if Basic Science is taught using appropriate methods, students' acquisition of Creative-Thinking-Fluency for idea creation and self-reliance in adulthood would be assumed.

One of the factors affecting creativity in general may be poor teaching method. Despite the need for Creative-Thinking-Fluency, there seem to be discrepancies between policy and implementation. It is lamentable that while educational bureaus produced textbooks, guidelines, and other instructional materials, Ode, Ayua and Alabi (2019) reported that teachers are yet to significantly embrace teaching creativity. Many teachers seem to be uncertain about how they could incorporate Creative-Thinking-Fluency fostering activities into their teaching. Teachers encountered difficulties in encouraging risk-taking creative behaviours, responding to student mistakes, coping with student diversity, and designing creative activities (Cheng, 2011). It is against this background that the study bids to investigate the effect of Creative-Teaching on Creative-Thinking-Fluency among different-ability upper-basic science students in Gboko, Benue State. Specifically, objectives for this study are listed under:

- i. To examine the mean difference in the Creative-Thinking-Fluency among different ability students taught Basic Science using Creative-Teaching and lecture method.
- ii. To find out the mean difference in the Creative-Thinking-Fluency between male and female students with different ability taught Basic Science using Creative-Teaching.

Research Questions

In view with the purpose, the following research questions were posed:

- i. What is the mean difference in the Creative-Thinking-Fluency among different ability students taught Basic Science using Creative-Teaching and lecture method?
- ii. What is the mean difference in the Creative-Thinking-Fluency between male and female students with different ability taught Basic Science using Creative-Teaching?

Research Hypotheses

Sequel to the purpose, the following hypotheses were formulated and tested at $p \leq 0.05$ α -level:

HO₁ There is no significant mean difference in the Creative-Thinking-Fluency among different ability students taught Basic Science using Creative-Teaching and lecture method.

HO₂ There is no significant mean difference in the Creative-Thinking-Fluency between male and female students with different ability taught Basic Science using Creative-Teaching.

This study is anchored on Piaget's (1957) theory of cognitive development, which deals with the nature of knowledge itself and how humans gradually come to acquire, construct, and use it. Certainly, the theory relates to Torrance Incubation Model of Creative-Teaching stages: heightening anticipation, deepening expectation and keeping it going which allow students with different ability to tickle the imagination, look beyond the information on the surface to find what is beneath it all, as a result gaining creative-thinking-fluency, finding and using resources for future visions

Empirically, Peng (2019) studied effects of creativity instruction in science on creative thinking in and science achievement in Chinese students and found that significant differences were found in the combined creative-thinking scores (fluency, flexibility, and originality) for the three TIPS items. However, there is a yawning gap since the study did not consider different ability students and was limited in terms of geographical scope. Hence the current study bid to investigate mean difference of creative-thinking-fluency scores among different ability students taught Basic Science using Creative-Teaching and lecture method in Gboko, Benue State. Arefi and Jalali (2016) examined Comparison of Creativity Dimensions (Fluency, Flexibility, Elaboration, Originality) between Bilingual Elementary Students (Azari language-Kurdish language) in Urmia City, Iran and found that the fluency dimension from creativity was significantly different between the two groups of bilingual students and significant differences in creativity scores based on gender. However, the study did not care for different ability students in Gboko. That is why the current study examined the mean difference between male and female creative-thinking-fluency scores among different ability students taught Basic Science using Creative-Teaching.

Methodology

A pre-test post-test quasi-experimental design was used for the study. After pre-test, the experimental group was taught concept of chemicals using Creative-Teaching (CT); while the control group was taught the same concept using Lecture Method (LM) for six weeks before post-test. A multistage sample of 70 Upper-Basic II students in two schools drawn from the population of 674 (356 males and 318 females) in seven government grants aided schools in Gboko township was used for the study. Torrance Test of Creative Thinking (TTCT-Figural B) was used for data

collection. Section ‘A’ collected students’ bio data; while section ‘B’ had three activities each lasting for 10 minutes with opportunity for multiple responses of ideas, to test students’ Creative-Thinking-Fluency in Basic Science. Students’ ability levels were based on previous term’s performance grades (high = A/B; average = C/D; low = E/F). TTCT-Figural B was validated and pilot-tested with reliability coefficient of 0.83 determined by a test-retest method with Pearson Product Moment Correlation. Both pre-test and post-test were administered under standard examination conditions. The research questions were answered using mean and hypotheses were tested at 0.05 α -level using two-way Analysis of covariance.

Result

The result of this study is presented in table 1-4 in the order of the research questions and the null hypotheses as follows:

Table 1: Mean and Standard Deviation of Creative-thinking-fluency Scores of students taught Basic Science using Lecture Method (LM) and those taught using Creative-Teaching (CT).

Ability Level	Sample (n)	Teaching Method	Fluency-Pretest		Fluency-Posttest		\bar{x} Gain	\bar{x} Gain Difference
			\bar{x}	SD	\bar{x}	SD		
High	14	LM	8.36	1.737	8.50	0.855	0.14	0.07
	14	CT	8.79	0.802	9.00	0.000	0.21	
Average	9	LM	8.67	1.000	8.67	1.000	0.00	0.27
	11	CT	8.73	0.905	9.00	0.000	0.27	
Low	12	LM	8.17	1.850	8.08	1.832	0.09	0.11
	10	CT	8.80	0.422	9.00	0.000	0.2	
Cluster		LM	8.4		8.4		0.08	0.17
		CT	8.8		9.0		0.23	

The result in Table 1 shows the pre-test Creative-Thinking-Fluency mean scores among different-ability students, between LM and CT with cluster means of 8.4 and 8.8. The Table also shows that all the Creative-Thinking-Fluency mean scores among different-ability students in the CT were higher than those in the LM with cluster mean gain difference of 0.17.

Table 2: Mean and Standard Deviation of Creative-thinking-fluency Scores of male and female students taught Basic Science using Creative-Teaching.

Ability Level	Sample (n)	Gender	Fluency-Pretest		Fluency-Posttest		\bar{x} Gain	\bar{x} Gain Difference
			\bar{x}	SD	\bar{x}	SD		
High	9	Male	9.00	.000	8.44	1.014	0.56	0.04
	19	Female	8.37	1.606	8.89	.315	0.52	
Average	10	Male	8.40	1.265	8.70	.949	0.30	0.30
	10	Female	9.00	.000	9.00	.000	0.00	
Low	12	Male	8.58	.900	8.75	.866	0.17	0.07
	10	Female	8.30	1.889	8.20	1.874	0.10	
Cluster		Male	8.66		8.63		0.34	0.14
		Female	8.56		8.70		0.21	

The result in Table 2 shows the pre-test mean scores among different-ability male and female students with cluster means of 8.66 and 8.56. The table also shows the Creative-Thinking-Fluency mean scores in the post test of male and female students with cluster mean gains of 0.34 and 0.21 respectively.

Table 3: Summary of Two-Way ANCOVA Analysis on Creative-Thinking-Fluency among Different-ability Levels Based on Teaching Methods.

Source	Type III Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	P	Partial Squared	Eta Noncent. Parameter	Observed Power ^b
Corrected Model	13.125 ^a	6	2.187	2.780	.018	.209	16.679	.846
Intercept	64.238	1	64.238	81.633	.000	.564	81.633	1.000
Fluency Pre-test	4.842	1	4.842	6.153	.016	.089	6.153	.685
Teaching Method	4.200	1	4.200	5.338	.024	.078	5.338	.624
Ability Level	.710	2	.355	.451	.639	.014	.902	.120
Teaching Method * Ability Level	.642	2	.321	.408	.667	.013	.816	.113
Error	49.575	63	.787					
Total	5361.000	70						
Corrected Total	62.700	69						

a. R Squared = .209 (Adjusted R Squared = .134)

Table 3 shows no significant difference in the Creative-Thinking-Fluency among different-ability students within those taught Basic Science using CT and those taught using LM, $F(2, 63) = 0.408, p(0.667) > 0.05$. Therefore, the null hypothesis was not rejected. However, the table showed that student's Creative-Thinking-Fluency in the CT was better than those in the LM $F(1, 63) = 5.338, p(0.024) < 0.05$. The implication of the result is that although Creative-Teaching enhances Creative-Thinking-Fluency, it is not dependent on students' academic ability.

Table 4: Summary of Two-Way ANCOVA Analysis on Creative-Thinking-Fluency among Different-ability Levels Based on Gender.

Source	Type III Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	P	Partial Squared	Eta Noncent. Parameter	Observed Power ^b
Corrected Model	11.943 ^a	6	1.990	2.471	.033	.190	14.824	.793
Intercept	54.707	1	54.707	67.903	.000	.519	67.903	1.000
Fluency Pre-test	7.205	1	7.205	8.942	.004	.124	8.942	.838
Gender	.147	1	.147	.183	.670	.003	.183	.071
Ability Level	.977	2	.488	.606	.549	.019	1.213	.147
Gender * Ability Level	3.438	2	1.719	2.134	.127	.063	4.267	.422
Error	50.757	63	.806					
Total	5361.000	70						
Corrected Total	62.700	69						

a. R Squared = .190 (Adjusted R Squared = .113)

Table 4 reveals that no significant difference existed in the Creative-Thinking-Fluency among different-ability male and female students taught Basic Science using CT, $F(2, 63) = 2.134, p(0.127) > 0.05$. The null hypothesis was therefore not rejected. This implies that, Creative-Teaching is without gender disparity, hence it enhances Creative-Thinking-Fluency in both male and female students with different-ability in Basic Science students.

Discussion

The result of the study shows no significant difference in the Creative-Thinking-Fluency scores among different-ability students. However, student's Creative-Thinking-Fluency in the Creative-Teaching was higher than those in the lecture method. With regards to field experience, the finding is not odd because students in the Creative-Teaching were engaged through heightening anticipation, deepening expectation and keeping it going to: tickle their imaginations, acquire and create ideas, look beyond the information on the surface to find what is beneath it all, construct their knowledge, and use resources for future visions. The finding disagrees with Peng (2019) who found significant differences in the combined creative-thinking scores (fluency, flexibility, and originality) for the three TIPS items. This may be due to variations in curriculum content, teaching strategy, location and probably time and the combined TIPS.

Based, on gender, findings of the study show no significant difference in the Creative-Thinking-Fluency scores between male and female students with different-ability levels taught Basic Science using Creative-teaching. This implies that, Creative-Teaching is without gender disparity across high, average and low ability students in Basic Science. Following field experience, the finding is not strange because both boys and girls explored their ideas, construct and use it for future visions through active involvement in Creative-Teaching and learning processes. Thus, the finding disagrees with Arefi and Jalali (2016) who found significant differences in creativity (fluency and originality) scores based on gender. This may also be due to variations in curriculum content, teaching strategy, location and probably time.

Conclusion and Recommendations

Based on the findings, it was concluded that: Creative-Thinking-Fluency among different-ability students may enhanced without gender disparity if taught Basic Science using Creative-Teaching. To do this effectively, the following were recommended:

1. Teachers not only at the upper basic school level, should be trained by the Federal, State Ministries of Education and other stakeholders through seminars, workshops on how to effectively utilize Creative-Teaching.
2. Government through the Ministries of Education and teacher training institutions in Nigeria should ensure in-service training and retraining of teachers to maximize Creative-Teaching lesson delivery.
3. Teacher training institutions in Nigeria should include constructive teaching strategies such as Creative-Teaching in the teacher training programmes
4. School proprietors, head and parents' teachers' association should provide materials/funds needed by the teachers for Creative-Teaching of Basic Science.

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